

S2 Supplementary Results

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This section presents the results generated through application of the EVRoN framework, providing an evidentiary basis for evaluating ecological integrity and constitutional thresholds under Articles 71–74 of the Ecuadorian Constitution.

Results are structured by levels of biological organisation (species to biome) to reflect how ecological evidence accumulates and informs trigger, precautionary, and potential violation thresholds. They integrate multiple data sources: the EIA¹ baseline, biospatial predictions, independent paraecologist-led field surveys and remote sensing and predictive modelling work. Analyses focused on translating ecological data into constitutionally relevant signals using the RoN Mapper and associated indicators, while also identifying evidentiary gaps between datasets. These gaps are treated as constitutionally material, particularly where uncertainty relates to extinction risk, ecosystem function, or biocultural relationships. Together, the results provide a multi-scalar assessment of ecological condition and evidentiary completeness, supporting evaluation of whether the EIA meets the requirements of a Rights of Nature compatible assessment.

The collated dataset for all species and their ecological attributes identified in the EIA, predictive biospatial analyses and our independent field surveys is available in this directory as ‘S2 Dataset 1 Species and Attributes’. Results of our independent field surveys and analyses are detailed below.

¹ *Fases de Explotación y Beneficio Del Área Operativa Del Proyecto Minero Warintza, Así Como Infraestructura Complementaria En Ella* (Unpublished report submitted to the Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica., 2024).

S2.1 Paraecologist field surveys

S2.1.1 Camera trapping for Medium- and large-sized mammals

A total of five orders (Didelphimorphia, Carnivora, Pilosa, Cingulata, Artiodactyla and Rodentia), 16 families and 25 species of mammals were recorded in the Maikiuants community, based on a sampling effort of 2 years and 4 months (equivalent to 18,240 observation hours) using six camera traps distributed across the Yunkumas and Aakas microcatchments. The trophic guilds comprised carnivores (eight species), omnivores (eleven species), herbivores (three species), frugivores (one species) and insectivores (two species).

Regarding conservation status, according to the national list (Tirira 2021), four species are classified as Vulnerable (VU): margay (*Leopardus wiedii*), jaguarundi (*Herpailurus yagouaroundi*), puma (*Puma concolor*), and bush dog (*Speothos venaticus*). Additionally, three species are classified as Endangered (EN): spectacled bear (*Tremarctos ornatus*), jaguar (*Panthera onca*), and giant anteater (*Myrmecophaga tridactyla*). The remaining species fall into less threatened categories.

Table S2.1.1. List of mammal species in Maikiuants territory, conservation categories and trophic guilds.

Order	Family	Species	Common names	IUCN	National	Trophic guild
Didelphimorphia	Didelphidae	<i>Didelphis marsupialis</i>	Common opossum / Black opossum	LC	LC	Omnivore
		<i>Marmosa</i> sp.	Mouse opossum	NA	NA	Omnivore
Carnivora	Felidae	<i>Leopardus wiedii</i>	Margay	NT	VU	Carnivore
		<i>Leopardus pardalis</i>	Ocelot	LC	NT	Carnivore
		<i>Panthera onca</i>	Jaguar	NT	EN	Carnivore
		<i>Herpailurus yagouaroundi</i>	Jaguarundi	NE	VU	Carnivore
		<i>Puma concolor</i>	Puma	LC	VU	Carnivore
	Mustelidae	<i>Eira barbara</i>	Tayra	LC	LC	Carnivore
		<i>Neogale frenata</i>	Long-tailed weasel	LC	LC	Carnivore

	Canidae	<i>Speothos venaticus</i>	Bush dog	NT	VU	Carnivore
	Procyonidae	<i>Nasua nasua</i>	Coati	LC	LC	Omnivore
		<i>Potos flavus</i>	Kinkajou	LC	LC	Omnivore
		<i>Procyon cancrivorus</i>	Crab-eating raccoon	LC	LC	Carnivore
	Ursidae	<i>Tremarctos ornatus</i>	Spectacled bear	VU	EN	Omnivore
Pilosa		<i>Tamandua tetradactyla</i>	Southern tamandua	LC	LC	Insectivore
	Myrmecophagidae	<i>Myrmecophaga tridactyla</i>	Giant anteater	VU	EN	Insectivore
Cingulata	Dasypodidae	<i>Dasybus novemcinctus</i>	Nine-banded armadillo	LC	LC	Omnivore
Artiodactyla	Cervidae	<i>Mazama americana</i>	Red brocket deer	DD	NT	Herbivore
	Tayassuidae	<i>Dicotyles tajacu</i>	Collared peccary	LC	NT	Omnivore
Rodentia	Sciuridae	<i>Hadroskiurus igniventris</i>	Amazon red squirrel	LC	LC	Frugivore
	Cuniculidae	<i>Cuniculus paca</i>	Paca	LC	NT	Herbivore
	Dasyproctidae	<i>Dasyprocta fuliginosa</i>	Agouti	LC	LC	Herbivore
	Cricetidae	<i>Neacomys amoenus</i>	Soft-furred mouse	LC	LC	Omnivore
	Sciuridae	<i>Microsciurus flaviventer</i>	Dwarf squirrel	LC	LC	Omnivore
	Cricetidae	<i>Hylaeamys perenensis</i>	Rice rat	LC	LC	Omnivore
	Echimyidae	<i>Proechimys</i> sp.	Spiny rat	LC	NT	Omnivore

2.1.2 Bat survey results

A total of 13 bat species were recorded during a preliminary (pilot) sampling effort. No conservation status is reported for these species.

Table 2.1.2. Preliminary list of bat species from the Maikiuants territory.

Order	Family	Species
Chiroptera	Phyllostomidae	<i>Anoura cultrata</i>
		<i>Artibeus lituratus</i>
		<i>Artibeus obscurus</i>
		<i>Artibeus planirostris</i>
		<i>Carollia brevicauda</i>
		<i>Carollia castanea</i>
		<i>Carollia perspicillata</i>
		<i>Chiroderma trinitatum</i>
		<i>Micronycteris megalotis</i>
		<i>Platyrrhinus ismaeli</i>
		<i>Sturnira giannae</i>
		<i>Sturnira oporaphilum</i>
	Molossidae	<i>Molossus molossus</i>

2.1.3 Richness and abundance of medium and large-sized mammals by microcatchment and altitudinal zone in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers (Maikiuants)

Table 2.1.3 shows variation in species richness in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers by altitude. In the upper zone, Yunkumas presents 20 species compared with 15 in Aakas. In the middle zone, Aakas declines to 6 species, whereas Yunkumas remains at 17. Overall, Yunkumas exceeds Aakas in richness at both altitudinal levels.

Table 2.1.3. Species richness, abundance, and diversity indices (Shannon and Simpson) in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers by altitudinal zone.

River	Zone	Species richness	Abundance	Shannon index	Simpson index
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Aakas	Upper	15	43	2.41	0.88
Aakas	Middle	6	9	1.74	0.81
Yunkumas	Upper	20	53	2.68	0.91
Yunkumas	Middle	17	110	2.11	0.81

Figure S2.1.1. Species richness across altitudinal zones (upper and middle) in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers. The x-axis labelled “Zona” (Spanish for zone) represents the altitudinal categories, while the y-axis labelled “Riqueza de especies” (species richness) indicates the number of species recorded.

Figure S2.1.2. Species abundance across altitudinal zones (upper and middle) in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers. The x-axis labelled “Zona” (Spanish for zone) represents the altitudinal categories, while the y-axis labelled “Abundancia de especies” (species abundance) indicates the total number of individual records.

S2.1.4 Amphibian transect survey results

A total of 27 amphibian species were recorded within the study area, distributed across 9 families and 19 genera. The Aakas micro-catchment exhibited the highest species richness, with 22 species recorded, whereas 16 species were documented in the Yunkumas micro-catchment. It should be noted that sampling effort was lower in the Yunkumas micro-catchment (Table S2.1.4). In terms of threat categories, 5% of species are classified as Near Threatened (NT), 85% as Least Concern (LC), and 10% as Data Deficient (DD). Approximately 25% of the amphibian species recorded within the community are endemic to Ecuador.

Species composition by transect: The table and the figures below present the results of amphibian surveys conducted in the Aakas and Yunkumas river micro-catchments, organised by transect (TA and TY). Species richness, abundance, and two diversity indices (Shannon and Simpson) are compared. In the Aakas micro-catchment, transect TA1 stands out, showing the highest species richness (21 species), greatest abundance (48 individuals), and the highest Shannon and Simpson index values, indicating high diversity. Transects TA2 and TA3 show a progressive decline across all parameters. In the Yunkumas micro-catchment, both transects (TY1 and TY2) exhibit intermediate and relatively stable values of species richness (9–10 species) and diversity. These values exceed those of the least diverse Aakas transects (TA2 and TA3) but remain substantially lower than those recorded at TA1.

Table S2.1.4. Species composition of amphibians in the Aakas and Yunkumas river micro-catchments in Maikiuants territory.

Code	River	Species richness	Abundance	Shannon index	Simpson index
TA1	Aakas	21	48	2.8168	0.9245
TA2	Aakas	8	11	1.8938	0.8099
TA3	Aakas	2	3	0.6365	0.4444
TY1	Yunkumas	10	23	1.7851	0.7335
TY2	Yunkumas	9	26	1.8926	0.8136

Figure S2.1.3. Comparison of species richness (*Riqueza*, left panel) and total abundance (*Abundancia_total*, right panel) across sampling stations (TA1–TA3 and TY1–TY2) in two rivers (Aakas, dark green; Yunkumas, light green).

Figure S2.1.4. Box-and-whisker plots of Shannon (left) and Simpson (right) diversity indices for assemblages in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers.

Alpha diversity

Diversity indices (Shannon and Simpson) in the microcatchments of the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers indicate moderate to high diversity. Yunkumas exhibits slightly higher values.

Figure S2.1.5. Boxplots of Shannon (left) and Simpson (right) diversity indices comparing assemblages in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers. The x-axis labelled “Río” (Spanish for river) indicates the two study systems, while the y-axes show the diversity metrics: “Shannon (H’)” for the Shannon index and “Simpson (1 – D)” for the Simpson index.

The following sections present the results of applying the Essential Variables for the Rights of Nature (EVRoN) framework to the EIA of the proposed Warintza mining project. The results are organised to reflect the structure of the methodological framework and the logic of Ecuador’s RoN jurisprudence, rather than conventional impact assessment reporting.

S2.2 EVRoN-Species: results

The collated dataset for all species and their ecological attributes identified in the EIA, predictive biospatial analyses and paraecologist field surveys is available in this directory as ‘S2 Dataset 1 Species and Attributes’. This includes the raw data for input to RoN Mapper (Species Input), the species data summary table (Table of Species and categories), the weightings applied to Biocultural Value (Biocultural weight table), Endangered species list, EDGE species list, a Keystone Species list, Key Biodiversity Area Indicator (KBA) Species list and a Biocultural species list.

The analysis begins with a summary of raw species-level results then metrics generated by the RoN Mapper, which constitute the formal procedure through which constitutional signals are identified, and the initial determination is made as to whether the EIA triggers heightened precautionary scrutiny. These results compare RoN signals derived from species data contained in the EIA alone with those generated using an expanded dataset incorporating biospatial predictions and our independent field surveys. Differences between these outputs are interpreted as constitutionally relevant evidentiary gaps rather than procedural shortcomings.

S2.2.1 Composition of the species-level evidentiary record

Analysis begins with a comparison of four distinct species-level datasets: (i) Species documented in the Warintza Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)², (ii) Biospatial analysis; species predicted as present within the project area based on global conservation species distribution datasets to assess how many species might have been missed by the EIA, (iii) Species identified through our independent field surveys led by Shuar paraecologists and our scientific team and, (iv) Bioculturally important species identified through our independent field survey.

The species records reported in the EIA constitute the formal biodiversity baseline available to regulatory authorities and document a total of 848 species, with species reported from biospatial analysis and our independent surveys summarised in Table S2.2.1.

² Lowell Mineral Exploration Ecuador S.A., *Estudio de Impacto Ambiental y Plan de Manejo Ambiental Para Las Fases de Explotación y Beneficio Del Área Operativa Del Proyecto Minero Warintza, Así Como Infraestructura Complementaria En Ella* (Unpublished report submitted to the Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica., 2024).

Figure S2.2.1. Venn-style schematic illustrating the overlap among species datasets derived from the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), biospatial modelling, and independent paraecologist-led field surveys. Biospatial modelling indicates that approximately 732 additional species may plausibly occur within the project area but are not represented in the EIA baseline, while site-verified field surveys confirm the presence of at least 127 species not recorded in the EIA. Collectively, the diagram demonstrates that the EIA baseline captures only a partial subset of species likely to be present within the project area, with limited overlap between EIA-reported species and both predicted and field-confirmed datasets (see Supplementary Results Table S2.1 for full disaggregated data across all datasets). Figure

Figure S2.2.2. Venn diagram illustrating overlap among extinction-threatened species (IUCN categories: Extinct in the Wild [EW], Critically Endangered [CR], Endangered [EN], and Vulnerable [VU]) identified across the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), biospatial analysis, and independent paraecologist-led field surveys. Biospatial modelling indicates that approximately 45 additional endangered species may plausibly occur within the project area but are not represented in the EIA baseline, while site-verified field surveys confirm the presence of 10 species not recorded in the EIA. Collectively, the diagram demonstrates that the EIA baseline captures only a partial subset of species at risk of extinction within the project area, with limited overlap between EIA-reported species and both predicted and field-confirmed datasets (see Supplementary Results Table S2.2 for full disaggregated data across all datasets)

Table S2.2.1. Number of species confirmed by the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), predicted using biospatial analysis and species identified from our independent surveys. The table summarises associated species-level attributes, including Evolutionarily Distinct and Globally Endangered (EDGE) species, Key Biodiversity Area (KBA) indicator species overlapping the impact area, keystone species, endemic species, new species records, IUCN extinction risk category (lowest of global or national status: EW, CR, EN, VU, DD, LC, NE), and total endangered species (EW–VU).

	Total Species	EDGE Species	KBA indicator Species	Keystone species	Endemic species	New Species	Biocultural	IUCN Extinction Risk Category								Total Endangered Species
								EW	CR	EN	VU	NT	DD	LC	NE	
EIA	848	2	7	4	35	0	360	0	0	9	31	28	10	491	279	40
Biospatial analysis	865	7	8	6	22	0	25	1	4	11	40	58	19	732	0	55
Paraecologist Field Survey	72	1	1	4	8	3	3	0	0	4	6	12	0	42	8	10
Biocultural species survey	103	0	0	0	4	0	103	1	0	2	2	1	4	39	54	4
All species	1697	8	11	8	50	3	469	2	4	21	66	76	31	1156	341	91

When the EIA baseline is integrated with biospatial analysis and paraecologist surveys, a total of 1,697 species records is generated. Within this assemblage, 93 species are classified as threatened with extinction, comprising 4 Critically Endangered (CR), 21 Endangered (EN), and 66 Vulnerable (VU) species, with an additional 76 Near Threatened (NT) and 31 Data Deficient (DD) species. Notably, two species are classified as Extinct in the Wild (EW). On the basis of raw species-level evidence alone, and prior to application of the RoN Mapper, the observed and predicted concentration of endangered and EDGE species is sufficient to activate constitutional scrutiny under Article 73 and warrant progression beyond species-level assessment.

Biospatial modelling outputs further indicate that approximately 732 additional species may plausibly occur within the project area but are not represented in the EIA baseline. Our independent field surveys undertaken for this assessment further confirm the presence of at least 127 species not recorded in the EIA. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that the EIA baseline captures only a partial subset of the species likely to be present within the project area (Figure 3; Supplementary Results Table S2.1).

Table S2.2.2. Species overlap among data sources. The table summarises the number of species occurring uniquely within, and shared among, biospatial predictions (Biospatial), the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), paraecologist surveys (ParaE), and the Biocultural Species Survey (2025). Each row represents a specific combination of data sources, with counts derived from presence–absence set intersections.

	Number of species
Biospatial	865
EIA	848
Biospatial \cap EIA	133
Biocultural Species Survey	103
ParaE	72
EIA \cap ParaE	31
Biospatial \cap ParaE	29
EIA \cap Biocultural Species Survey 5	17
Biospatial \cap EIA \cap ParaE	17

Table S2.2.3. Species overlap among data sources for IUCN endangered species for the datasets.

	Number of species
Biospatial	56
EIA	40
Biospatial \cap EIA	11
ParaE	10
Biospatial \cap ParaE	5
EIA \cap ParaE	5
Biospatial \cap EIA \cap ParaE	3
Biocultural Species Survey	5

Analysis of data provenance indicates that most extinction-threatened species are not documented within the EIA baseline. Of the species threatened with extinction, identified across the expanded dataset, an additional 9% are confirmed exclusively through our field surveys, while a further 46% are predicted through biospatial analysis, but remain unaccounted for in the EIA (Figure S2.2.2; Table S2.2.3). This limited overlap indicates that the EIA captures only a minor subset of RoN-salient threatened taxa, while most extinction-relevant species remain invisible within the formal regulatory record.

From a constitutional perspective, this evidentiary gap is material, as Article 73 does not require complete certainty, but only a plausible risk of extinction to activate mandatory precaution.

Beyond extinction risk, the expanded dataset identifies eight Evolutionarily Distinct and Globally Endangered (EDGE) species, whose loss would entail irreversible erosion of irreplaceable evolutionary and genetic heritage protected under Article 71. The presence of such species narrows the scope of lawful restoration under Article 72 and meets the low evidentiary threshold for precaution under Article 73. In these circumstances, constitutionally adequate assessment requires population-level modelling to evaluate viability and recovery potential. The absence of EVRoN Population-level analysis in the EIA therefore constitutes a material evidentiary gap, necessitating escalation beyond species-level assessment³.

³ Corte Constitucional del Ecuador, *Sentencia No. 1149-19-JP/21* (Bosque Protector Los Cedros), 10 Nov 2021, paras 25–28, 65, 131–142; *Sentencia A'i Cofán de Sinangoe*, 27 Jan 2022.

The expanded dataset includes 11 Key Biodiversity Area (KBA) indicator species and 50 regional or national endemics, which heighten constitutional concern under Article 71 by virtue of their restricted geographic distributions and ecological non-substitutability. Of greater concern, our independent field surveys identified three candidate new (undescribed) species that are taxonomically distinct and currently undergoing formal description. The presence of previously undocumented taxa reveals material epistemic limitations in the EIA evidence base and engages the precautionary obligations of Article 73, which are activated by plausible risks to ecological integrity notwithstanding scientific uncertainty. Of particular significance is an undescribed species of the genus *Rhinella*, provisionally associated with the Maikiuants territory and representing the first species formally collected and identified by a Shuar paraecology team. To date, this species has been recorded exclusively from the summit of a geographically isolated cloud-forest peak located adjacent to the proposed mining activity, a circumstance that both constrains the scope of lawful restoration under Article 72 and amplifies concern regarding irreversible ecological loss.

In parallel, 469 species were identified as having utilitarian and/or biocultural significance, with 18 of those designated as of sacred significance, directly engaging Article 74, which protects relational ecological values and culturally embedded human-nature relationships. Harm to such species cannot be meaningfully mitigated or compensated through technical measures and therefore constitutes an independent constitutional constraint on authorisation, irrespective of extinction risk.

A further point is the high proportion of records within the EIA that are not identified to species level. Of the 848 biodiversity records reported in the EIA, 156 records (18%) lack species-level identification. This lack of taxonomic resolution indicates either insufficient taxonomic rigour in survey and reporting practices or the presence of a substantial number of undescribed taxa within the sampled area. In either case, the absence of species-level identification limits the ability of decision-makers to assess extinction risk or irreversible harm, thereby reinforcing the application of precaution where uncertainty persists.

Taken together, and without reliance on exhaustive species enumeration, the results demonstrate that trigger, precautionary, and potential violation thresholds under Articles 71-74 are engaged, predominantly by species not captured in the EIA baseline. This pattern is constitutionally material as it shows that the current EIA evidence base is insufficient to establish compatibility with the RoN, and that uncertainty must be resolved *in dubio pro natura* rather than in favour of authorisation.

S2.2.2 EVRoN-Species: Rights of Nature Mapper (RoN Mapper) signals

Comparison of RoN Mapper outputs across the species datasets reveals substantial variation in both the extent and intensity of constitutionally relevant signals, depending on data provenance (Table S2.4.1). These differences demonstrate that the scope and distribution of RoN risks are highly sensitive to the evidentiary basis used, with marked implications for EIA adequacy.

RoN Mapper analysis of the EIA baseline dataset identifies 56 Constitutionally Imperilled Ambassador Species (CIAS), representing 7% of species analysed. While this dataset activates a substantial number of threshold exceedances under Articles 72 and 73, it exhibits relatively low mean values for both the Rights of Nature Linkage Index (RLI = 0.12) and the Species Rights Risk Score (SRRS = 13.2). This indicates that, although the EIA captures some constitutionally salient risks, it provides a comparatively limited representation of their intensity and distribution.

Table S2.4.1. Comparative summary of Rights of Nature (RoN) Mapper outputs across datasets. The table reports, for each dataset, the number and proportion of species identified as Constitutionally Imperilled Species (CIS) or Constitutionally Imperilled Ambassador Species (CIAS), together with mean Rights of Nature Linkage Index (RLI) and mean Species Rights Risk Score (SRRS). The final columns show the number of species exceeding constitutional thresholds under Articles 71-74 of the Ecuadorian Constitution. Results are disaggregated by data provenance (EIA baseline, biospatial analysis, paraecologist-led field surveys, and biocultural analysis), highlighting differences in constitutional signal strength and evidentiary completeness between formally assessed (EIA) and supplementary datasets.

Dataset	RoN Mapper species identified/total species analysed (percentage)		Mean Rights of Nature Linkage Index (RLI)	Mean Species Rights Risk Score (SRRS)	Species Counts per Article (>Threshold)			
	CIS species	CIAS species			Article 71	Article 72	Article 73	Article 74
EIA	-	56/848 (7%)	0.12	13.2	9	43	40	11
Biospatial Analysis	85/865 (10%)	-	0.18	5.0	12	60	55	25
Independent Field Survey (Paraecologists)	-	14/72 (19%)	0.4	13.3	5	11	10	3
Biocultural Field Survey	-	103/103 (100%)	1.08	40.7	0	4	4	103
Biospatial Analysis minus those in EIA	50/732 (7%)	-	0.14	4.4	8	48	44	1
Independent Field Survey minus those in EIA	-	5/41 (12%)	0.27	12.3	1	5	5	0
Biocultural Field Survey minus those in EIA		34/86 (39%)	0.44	34.7	0	4	4	30

Biospatial analysis, excluding species already reported in the EIA, identifies a similar proportion of Constitutionally Imperilled Species (CIS) (50/732; 7 %) and numerous additional threshold exceedances under Articles 72 and 73, despite a lower mean SRRS (4.4). This pattern indicates the presence of latent constitutional exposure not documented in the EIA baseline, arising from species plausibly present but not identified from EIA fieldwork. These species should be the focus of further field survey to confirm their presence or absence.

Species identified exclusively through our field surveys exhibit a higher relative concentration of Constitutionally Imperilled Ambassador Species (CIAS) (5/41; 12 %), together with markedly elevated mean RLI (0.27) and SRRS values, despite smaller absolute species counts. This pattern might reflect disproportionate constitutional salience of intensified field sampling, which is necessary to detect rarer species whose attributes are more likely to be associated with irreversible or non-substitutable ecological and biocultural harm.

The biocultural dataset identifies a high proportion of Constitutionally Imperilled Ambassador Species (CIAS) (34/86; 39 %) and exhibits the highest mean values for both RLI (0.44) and SRRS (34.7). These results are characterised by a greater frequency of threshold activation under Article 74, indicating that species associated with biocultural datasets account for a substantial share of system-level constitutional signals observed in the analysis.

Taken together, the results demonstrate that exclusive reliance on the EIA baseline systematically understates RoN risks, both in scope and intensity. Supplementary biospatial, field-confirmed, and biocultural datasets consistently intensify constitutional scrutiny across multiple articles, highlighting evidentiary incompleteness in the current EIA.

Population-Risk Constitutionally Imperilled Ambassador Species: Across datasets, RoN Mapper identifies a subset of CIAS characterised by confirmed presence and attributes whose loss would entail disproportionate, irreversible, or non-substitutable harm, including keystone and EDGE species engaging Articles 71 and 73, and, in some cases, Article 74. Within this group, 50 CIAS listed as Critically Endangered, Endangered, or Vulnerable under the IUCN Red List are classified as Population-Risk Constitutionally Imperilled Ambassador Species (PR-CIAS; Supplementary Datasets S2 PR CIAS species list) and should be the subject of review at the next level of biological organisation (EVRoN-Population).

Biocultural relationships as a distinct constitutional domain: Article 74 of the Ecuadorian Constitution affirms the right of people and communities to benefit from Nature in ways that respect and sustain ecological cycles and functions. Unlike Articles 71-73, which emphasise ecological integrity, restoration, and precaution, Article 74 explicitly recognises the relational dimension of human-nature interactions. Under a RoN framework, biocultural values are therefore not ancillary but constitute an independent dimension of constitutional relevance.

The case study identified 469 species as having biocultural importance through combined paraecologist fieldwork and EIA-derived data, capturing species embedded in Shuar cultural,

subsistence, and territorial practices. Within this set, 15 species are classified as threatened (CR, EN, VU) or Extinct in the Wild (EW), including sacred species such as *Brugmansia suaveolens* (EW) and *Panthera onca* (EN) (Table S2.4.2.). In parallel, 147 species were identified as ecologically important (e.g. as trophic resources), providing a proxy for community-level ecological knowledge. Together, these datasets demonstrate that ecological change affects not only biodiversity but also constitutionally protected relationships between communities and ecosystems.

Table S2.4.2. Bioculturally important species identified through fieldwork and secondary sources, ranked by conservation status (Extinct in the Wild to Vulnerable). The table highlights species with documented cultural significance (including sacred status), alongside their taxonomic affiliation, endemism, and IUCN Red List category, to support integrated assessment of biocultural value and conservation risk within the EVRoN framework.

Species	Common name	Local name	Family	Sacred	IUCN	Endemism	Source ¹
<i>Brugmansia suaveolens</i>	Angel's trumpet	Floripondio	Solanaceae	✓	EW	–	Biocultural Fieldwork
<i>Panthera onca</i>	Jaguar	Jaguar	Felidae	✓	EN	–	Biospatial; EIA; ParaE
<i>Cinchona cf. mutisii</i>	Cinchona tree	Cinchona	Rubiaceae	–	EN	–	EIA
<i>Guatteria ecuadorensis</i>	Guatteria	Palo Yais	Annonaceae	–	EN	National	Biocultural Fieldwork
<i>Inga multicaulis</i>	Inga	Sampi	Fabaceae	–	EN	National	Biocultural Fieldwork
<i>Licania aff. megalophylla</i>	Licania	Corocillo	Chrysobalanaceae	–	EN	–	EIA
<i>Anthurium subandinum</i>	Anthurium	Eepe	Araceae	✓	VU	National	Biocultural Fieldwork
<i>Cedrela fissilis</i>	Argentine cedar	Cedro	Meliaceae	–	VU	–	EIA
<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	Spanish cedar	Cedro rojo	Meliaceae	–	VU	–	Biospatial
<i>Miconia jorgensenii</i>	Miconia	Mora	Melastomataceae	–	VU	–	EIA
<i>Nectandra reflexa</i>	–	Canelo	Lauraceae	–	VU	–	EIA
<i>Ocotea ucayalensis</i>	–	–	Lauraceae	–	VU	–	EIA
<i>Persea raimondii</i>	–	Aguacatillo	Lauraceae	–	VU	–	EIA
<i>Pleurothyrium williamsii</i>	–	–	Lauraceae	–	VU	–	EIA
<i>Tillandsia rhodosticta</i>	Air plant	Kuishop 2	Bromeliaceae	–	VU	National	Biocultural Fieldwork

¹ Source index;

EIA: (Lowell Mineral Exploration Ecuador S.A., *Estudio de Impacto Ambiental y Plan de Manejo Ambiental Para Las Fases de Explotación y Beneficio Del Área Operativa Del Proyecto Minero Warintza, Así Como Infraestructura Complementaria En Ella* (Unpublished report submitted to the Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica., 2024).

Biospatial: Predictive species presence analysis - Supplementary methods S1.1.

Biocultural Field Survey: Fieldwork S1.3.4 Biocultural value - study design and conceptual framework

Biocultural EVRoN and Rights of Nature thresholds: Within the EVRoN framework, biocultural variables occupy a distinct analytical position. While quantified through structured scoring to support comparison, their constitutional role is not reducible to metrics. Instead, they operate as qualitative constitutional triggers, identifying forms of harm that are non-substitutable and potentially irreversible in social-ecological terms.

The presence of threatened and sacred species (*Panthera onca*, *Brugmansia suaveolens*, *Anthurium subandinum*) alongside endemic taxa (e.g. *Guatteria ecuadorensis*, *Inga multicaulis*), indicates that impacts may exceed ecological thresholds by disrupting relational systems tied to place, identity, and practice. These risks require an escalation to EVRoN-Population level assessment, where species at risk of extinction can be evaluated in terms of population viability and project-specific pressures.

In constitutional terms, disruption of biocultural relationships engages a precautionary logic analogous to Article 73 but grounded in relational irreversibility. Once lost, these relationships cannot be restored through ecological mitigation alone, limiting the adequacy of standard EIA assumptions regarding compensability and restoration.

Indigenous knowledge as constitutional evidence: The paraecologist and community data underpinning the identification of biocultural EVRoN constitutes constitutionally relevant evidence, rather than supplementary information. Shuar knowledge documents species not only as biological entities but as components of lived systems of meaning, use, and responsibility. This is particularly significant in relation to the 147 species identified as ecologically important, which function as a proxy for community-level ecological knowledge and system understanding. Such knowledge provides insight into ecological processes (e.g. trophic relationships) that are not fully captured in technical assessments, reinforcing its relevance to Articles 71-73 as well as Article 74. By situating ecological change within lived experience, paraecologist knowledge enables decision makers to evaluate impacts in terms of both ecological integrity and relational continuity, bridging the gap between scientific assessment and constitutional interpretation.

Constitutional implications of biocultural EVRoN: Comparison between EIA documentation and paraecologist-derived biocultural EVRoN reveals a clear constitutional evidence gap. While the EIA references cultural context, it does not generate the evidence required to assess how project activities affect biocultural relationships in line with Article 74. This omission has direct implications. Without explicit identification of biocultural EVRoN, impacts to species such as Jaguar (*Panthera onca*) risk being treated as isolated biodiversity concerns, rather than as constitutionally significant relational harms engaging Articles 71-74. Similarly, impacts to ecologically important species may degrade knowledge systems and stewardship capacity, an effect not captured in conventional assessments. These risks are further illustrated by observed socio-economic change in the neighbouring community of Warintz, where anecdotal evidence indicates a shift away from forest garden cultivation toward reliance on imported food enabled by mining income. This transition reflects a decoupling of livelihoods from local ecosystems,

signalling erosion of daily ecological interaction and knowledge transmission. Such processes constitute a form of relational harm, occurring even in advance of measurable biodiversity loss, and directly implicating Articles 71 and 74.

The biocultural results highlight the limits of conventional EIA frameworks in capturing the full scope of constitutionally protected human-nature relationships. In the Warintza case, the identification of 469 bioculturally important species, 15 of which are threatened, together with 147 ecologically significant species, demonstrates that impacts extend beyond biodiversity metrics to include relational, cultural, and knowledge-based dimensions. The findings reinforce that RoN compliance cannot be assessed solely through ecological indicators but must also account for the relational integrity of human-nature systems, particularly where high-risk species require escalation to EVRoN-Population level analysis.

S2.2.3 Constitutional implications of species-level evidence

Even at the level of the raw species dataset, prior to its formal translation through the RoN Mapper, the high number of endangered species recorded for the site, the absence of species-level identifications in the EIA, and the addition of new species identified through independent surveys, together with the substantial number of species identified in biospatial analyses but omitted from the EIA, are sufficient to trigger constitutional scrutiny under Article 73. This alone meets the applicable precautionary threshold recognised in Constitutional Court jurisprudence and supports escalation beyond a species-level assessment.

Comparison between RoN-Mapper outputs derived from EIA-only data and those derived from the expanded species dataset reveals a clear constitutional evidence gap. This gap is not attributable to procedural error within the EIA, but to a structural mismatch between the evidentiary demands of RoN law and the limited scope of species-level information typically produced in impact assessments.

From a constitutional perspective, the absence of species attribute data capable of triggering precautionary or violation thresholds from the EIA record does not negate the existence of such thresholds; rather, it renders them invisible to regulatory decision-makers. The RoN-Mapper makes this invisibility explicit by demonstrating that, under a RoN framework, species presence data, when integrated with species-specific criteria that connect to extinction risk (IUCN category, endemism, Key Biodiversity Area indicator), evolutionary potential (EDGE species), ecosystem structure and function (Keystone species) and biocultural importance, drawn from a broader evidentiary base, are sufficient to activate duties of precaution, avoidance, or refusal that are not apparent from EIA data alone.

S2.3. Population-level requirements (EVRoN–Population)

S2.3.1 Evidentiary basis

Section 6.2 establishes that the co-occurrence of 50 PR-CIAS species, 15 threatened bioculturally important taxa, three potentially new amphibian species, and 156 unidentified records (18% of EIA data) constitutes a conservative trigger for population-level assessment under EVRoN. This supplementary section does not repeat that finding but clarifies two elements not fully elaborated in the main text (i) Taxonomic uncertainty as a risk multiplier: the 156 unidentified records are not simply incomplete data; they represent unresolved biodiversity that may include additional range-restricted or at-risk taxa, and (ii) Priority structuring: while Section 6.2 identifies amphibians as a dominant risk group, it does not explicitly state that they should be treated as the primary entry point for population-level modelling. This follows from their high rates of endemism and narrow distributions within the dataset.

S2.3.2 Analytical requirements need for EIA compliance

Section 6.2 identifies the absence of population-level modelling as a critical omission but does not define the minimum analytical components required. For EVRoN-consistent implementation, population-level assessment should include:

- Distribution analysis (extent of occurrence; area of occupancy)
- Abundance or density estimation, where feasible
- Population structure and connectivity, including fragmentation risks
- Population viability analysis (PVA) under project-relevant scenarios
- Spatial overlap assessment between populations and:
 - the ~20 km² disturbance footprint over the 22-year operational period
 - associated infrastructure
 - downstream hydrological pathways (including AMD and tailings failure risk)

In addition, newly identified taxa require taxonomic resolution and baseline ecological characterisation prior to inclusion in formal modelling, an implicit requirement in Section 6.2 that is made explicit here.

S2.3.3 Unresolved evidentiary gaps

While Section 6.2 frames the absence of population-level analysis as constitutionally material, the specific components of that absence are not itemised. The following gaps remain:

- No species-specific viability assessments
- No quantification of population proportion exposed to project impacts
- No treatment of unidentified records as uncertainty-bearing risk
- No hydrologically extended impact modelling for aquatic systems (cross-referenced in Sections 6.3.4 and 6.5.2)

- No scenario-based risk modelling (e.g. chronic AMD, tailings failure events)

These omissions are particularly acute for amphibians, where Section 6.2 notes that 13 of 15 endangered PR-CIAS taxa are regional or national endemics, but does not explicitly link this to the likelihood that the project footprint may coincide with a substantial fraction of global populations.

S2.3.4 Clarification of scale and precaution

Section 6.2 correctly identifies that extinction risk operates at the population level. This section refines that point by distinguishing between absence of evidence at the wrong scale (species presence data), and absence of evidence at the required scale (population viability and distribution). The current EIA falls into the latter category. This is not a question of incomplete detail, but of analytical misalignment with the scale at which extinction risk is determined.

The presence of range-restricted amphibians, potentially undescribed taxa, and unresolved records means that extinction risk cannot be evaluated, not merely that it is uncertain.

S2.3.5 Supplementary conclusion

Consistent with Section 6.2, but extending its analytical precision, this supplementary analysis confirms that; (i) the requirement for population-level assessment under EVRoN is triggered and mandatory, (ii) the current evidentiary record lacks both modelling and the framework necessary to conduct it, and (iii) uncertainty (especially unidentified taxa) is risk-bearing and not neutral.

Accordingly, the absence of population-level evidence should be understood as a structural evidentiary deficiency, reinforcing, rather than merely supporting, the precautionary threshold identified under Article 73. Population-level ecological analysis therefore remains a precondition for lawful decision-making, as Section 6.2 concludes, but is here specified in terms of its required analytical components and unresolved gaps.

S2.4 Community-level evidence (EVRoN–Community): aquatic datasets

S2.4.1 EIA aquatic macroinvertebrate community results

A total of 14 sampling sites (MCR-01 to MCR-14) were surveyed within the EIA study area (April–May 2024), yielding 2956 individuals, classified into 3 phyla, 4 classes, 12 orders, 50 families, and 82 morphospecies. Macroinvertebrate indices were calculated for each site.

Table S2.4.1. Summary of macroinvertebrate indices (BMWP/Col, AAMBI, and EPT) across sampling sites (MCR-01 to MCR-14) in the EIA for the Warintza study area (Apr-May 2024). Mean values and 95% confidence intervals (CI) are presented.

Site	BMWP/Col ⁴	AAMBI ⁵	EPT (%) ⁶
MCR-01	131	123	67
MCR-02	173	141	35
MCR-03	171	147	61
MCR-04	160	145	34
MCR-05	129	105	38
MCR-06	104	93	28
MCR-07	163	143	57
MCR-08	97	89	14
MCR-09	125	115	88
MCR-10	136	122	65
MCR-11	116	112	76
MCR-12	147	133	47
MCR-13	167	142	67
MCR-14	192	164	67
Mean ± 95% CI	144 (127-160)	127 (114 - 139)	53.14 (41-65)

Notes: BMWP/Col = Biological Monitoring Working Party (Colombian adaptation); AAMBI = Andean–Amazon Biotic Index; EPT = percentage of Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera, and Trichoptera. Values are presented per sampling site; mean values include 95% confidence intervals calculated using Student’s *t*-distribution (*n* = 14).

Interpretation summary for streams and rivers sampled in the EIA

BMWP/Col (144): Indicates overall good to very good water quality

⁴ Lowell Mineral Exploration Ecuador S.A., *Estudio de Impacto Ambiental y Plan de Manejo Ambiental Para Las Fases de Explotación y Beneficio Del Área Operativa Del Proyecto Minero Warintza, Así Como Infraestructura Complementaria En Ella* (Unpublished report submitted to the Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica., 2024). Pages 676-677

⁵ As above Pages 677-678

⁶ As Above Pages 678-679

AAMBI (127): Consistent with high ecological integrity (excellent conditions)

EPT (53%): Suggests moderate-to-good ecological condition, with variability across sites suggested due to natural variability

S2.4.2 Independent survey aquatic macroinvertebrate community, water quality and riverine structure results

The results of the paraecologist macroinvertebrate study in the Aakas and Yunkumas rivers recorded a total of 2845 individuals belonging to three Phylum (Arthropoda, Annelida, Platyhelmintha), five Classes (Hirudinia, Oligochaeta, Arachnida, Turbellaria and Insecta), 13 orders and 44 families.

Table S2.4.2 Physico-chemical water parameters, macroinvertebrate indices (AAMBI, and EPT) and stream and riparian indices (IHF, QBR) with summary statistics across sampling sites in our independent surveys of rivers within Maikiuants. Mean values and 95% confidence intervals (CI) are presented.

Site	Flow rate (m ³ /s)	pH	DO (mg/L)	Conductivity (µS/cm)	Temperature (°C)	IHF	QBR	AAMBI
AE1	0.32	6.9	8.7	25	18.3	49	100	121
AE2	0.54	6.9	8.6	33	18.6	49	100	98
AE3	4.49	6.6	8.8	25	19.6	51	85	109
YE1	1.60	6.6	8.7	32	18.2	55	100	114
YE2	3.90	6.6	8.5	34	18.5	54	100	131
YE3	0.80	6.7	8.5	36	19.1	53	100	129
YE4	4.10	6.74	8.3	37	20.5	52	85	131
Coangos	—	7.23	8.8	36	22.0	—	80	—

Summary statistics (mean ± 95% CI)

Variable	Mean	95% CI
Flow rate (m ³ /s)	2.25	0.55 – 3.95
pH	6.78	6.60 – 6.97
DO (mg/L)	8.61	8.47 – 8.76
Conductivity (µS/cm)	32.25	28.26 – 36.24

Temperature (°C)	19.35	18.25 – 20.45
IHF	51.86	49.69 – 54.02
QBR	93.75	86.42 – 101.08
AAMBI	119.00	107.31 – 130.69

(— = *not measured*)

Note: IHF as low values because the river beds have very large rocks, not due to alteration. The index does not adjust for this type of river.

Table S2.4.3. Physico-chemical parameters measured in independently sampled water samples

Code	Chlorides (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Phosphate (mg/L)	Sulfate (mg/L)	Zinc (mg/L)	Lead mg/L	Cadmium mg/L	Copper (mg/L)
AE1	1.890	—	0.462	—	1.102	—	—	—	—
AE2	1.804	—	0.566	—	1.166	—	—	—	—
AE3	2.305	—	0.553	—	0.830	—	—	—	—
YE2	1.391	—	0.093	—	0.595	—	—	—	—
YE3	1.882	—	0.549	—	0.515	—	—	—	—
YE4	1.486	—	0.487	—	0.647	—	—	—	—
Coangos	1.568	—	0.715	—	1.421	0.021	—	—	—
Mean	1.761	—	0.489	—	0.897	0.021	—	—	—
(95% CI)	(1.474– 2.048)		(0.311– 0.667)		(0.582– 1.211)	(n=1)			

'—' below detection limit or not detected. Detection limits (mg/L): Chlorides 0.004, Nitrite 0.006, Nitrate 0.008, Phosphate 0.010, Sulphate 0.009, Zinc 0.012, Lead 0.094, Cadmium 0.038, Copper 0.038.

Concentrations of major ions were generally low, with mean ($\pm 95\%$ CI) chloride 1.76 mg/L (1.47–2.05), nitrate 0.49 mg/L (0.31–0.67), and sulphate 0.90 mg/L (0.58–1.21), while nitrite, phosphate, lead, cadmium and copper were consistently below detection limits; zinc was only detected at a single site (0.021 mg/L).

Table S2.4.4. Projected Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) impacts and their constitutional significance under Articles 71-74.

Finding (from EIA)	Constitutional article(s) engaged	Nature of engagement	Implication for long-term management
Majority (75%) of waste rock classified as potentially acid generating (PAG), with kinetic tests predicting short- to medium-term acid drainage	Art. 71; Art. 73	Risk of persistent alteration of aquatic chemistry and ecosystem processes; plausible irreversible harm	Precautionary and avoidance duties triggered; mitigation alone constitutionally insufficient
Predicted acidic leachate (pH ~4.3) from WRF with metal exceedances (Al, Ba, Co, Mn, Hg, Se, sulphate)	Art. 71; Art. 73	Threat to ecological integrity and natural cycles; chronic contamination risk	Requires long-term containment and monitoring, indicating non-temporary harm
Pit overflow predicted to be acidic (pH ~5.3) with copper exceedances	Art. 71; Art. 73	Ongoing source of metal loading to surface waters	Long-term management obligation persists beyond operations
Reliance on engineered containment, monitoring, and treatment “if necessary”	Art. 73; Art. 72 (constraint)	Post-impact control model accepted despite acknowledged risk	Restoration to pre-impact conditions biologically uncertain or infeasible
Risk of contaminant migration to surface water bodies (streams, rivers)	Art. 71; Art. 73	Potential ecosystem-level harm extending beyond project site	Cumulative and downstream impacts must be constitutionally assessed
Groundwater contamination risk managed primarily through monitoring wells	Art. 73	Detection-based strategy does not prevent irreversible harm	Precaution requires stricter safeguards than monitoring alone
Persistent contamination risks over operational and post-closure periods	Art. 72	Right of Nature to restoration materially constrained	Indicates need for perpetual management rather than restoration
Potential impacts on community water resources and aquatic food webs	Art. 74	Harm to relational (biocultural) human–nature values	Independent constitutional constraint on authorisation
Cumulative ecological risks in a biologically sensitive and diverse area	Art. 71; Art. 73	Reduced ecosystem resilience and adaptive capacity	Heightened constitutional scrutiny required

S2.4.3 Supporting detail: EIA-derived indices

Section 6.3.2 presents summary results of EIA-derived indices. This section provides supporting quantitative detail and clarification of interpretation rather than repeating those results. The dataset comprises 2956 individuals across 82 morphospecies and 50 families, forming the basis for BMWP/Col, AAMBI, and EPT calculations. Reported variation in EPT scores is attributed in the EIA to natural environmental heterogeneity; however, no formal analysis is presented to distinguish natural variability from early-stage disturbance signals. The classification of ‘good to very good’ and ‘excellent’ conditions is based on index thresholds, but the EIA does not explicitly contextualise these against reference (undisturbed) conditions in comparable catchments limiting the scope of future ability to assess impacts from proposed mining activity (i.e. BACI experimental design). These gaps do not contradict the high-quality classification reported in Section 6.3.2, but they indicate limits in interpretive resolution.

S2.4.4 Supporting detail: independent survey data

Section 6.3.3 reports independent survey findings indicating high ecological condition. This section adds methodological and interpretive clarification. Taxonomic coverage differs slightly from the EIA dataset (e.g., inclusion of additional classes such as Turbellaria) but remains functionally comparable at the family-level resolution used for index scoring. Physicochemical parameters reported in Section 6.3.3 are consistent with reference-condition rivers.

Low nutrient and metal concentrations, including non-detects for key pollutants, represent not only good condition, but absence of detectable anthropogenic influence. Together, these details reinforce the interpretation of near-reference ecological integrity, rather than simply ‘good’ condition.

S2.4.5 Analytical clarification

Section 6.3.4 establishes the EVRoN interpretation and constitutional implications of high-integrity aquatic systems. This section clarifies two analytical points that are implicit but not fully specified

1. Baseline condition as a legal threshold: The main text recognises that high integrity elevates the threshold for permissible impact. This section clarifies that: Index values (AAMBI, BMWP/Col, EPT), when consistent across independent datasets, function as evidence of reference or near-reference state, such states should be treated as baseline conditions for non-degradation, not simply as favourable existing conditions.
2. Integration of AMD risk pathways with baseline condition. Section 6.3.4 discusses AMD risks in legal terms. Here it is clarified that: The significance of AMD projections (acidic leachate, metal mobilisation) lies not only in their magnitude, but in their contrast with current baseline conditions, This contrast represents a potential state shift (from near-pristine to chemically altered system), rather than incremental degradation. This

distinction sharpens the conclusion that impact characterisation must be qualitative (state change), not only quantitative (degree of change).

S2.4.6 Residual analytical gaps

While Section 6.3 establishes the constitutional implications of community-level evidence, several technical gaps within the current EIA were unarticulated:

- No longitudinal (temporal) data to assess seasonal or interannual variability
- No integration of biological indices with predictive contamination modelling (e.g., AMD dispersion scenarios)
- Limited explicit linkage between community-level integrity and downstream/catchment-scale processes in EIA (to address issues raised in Sections 6.3.4 and 6.5)

These do not undermine the core finding of high integrity but are relevant to future monitoring and impact prediction requirements.

S2.4.7 Supplementary conclusion

Consistent with Section 6.3.5, both datasets support a finding of high ecological integrity and near-reference conditions. This supplementary analysis adds that the dual-dataset approach strengthens evidentiary robustness, observed conditions reflect absence of detectable anthropogenic disturbance, rather than merely acceptable status, and the contrast between current baseline and projected AMD risks represents a potential system-level transition, not incremental change. Accordingly, and in line with Section 6.3.5, aquatic community-level evidence should be interpreted as establishing a high-sensitivity baseline, reinforcing the requirement for precaution, avoidance, and heightened scrutiny under the Rights of Nature framework.

S2.5 Ecosystem-level evidence (EVRoN-Ecosystem): Forest integrity and territorial governance

S2.5.1 Forest ecosystems as constitutional objects of protection

For the purposes of the supplementary analysis, forest ecosystems in the Amazonian foothills of south-eastern Ecuador are treated as integrated socio-ecological systems where forest integrity and landscape connectivity operate as legally relevant indicators for assessing compliance with constitutional standards⁷. Where ecosystems exhibit a high degree of structural continuity, the applicable standard is orientated toward prevention of disturbance rather *than post hoc* restoration⁸.

This supplementary analysis therefore focuses on the spatial and governance conditions that underpin ecological integrity, rather than reiterating descriptive metrics presented in the main Results section. The evidentiary basis comprises an integrated assessment drawing on Indigenous territorial planning instruments, field observations, and remote sensing outputs, enabling cross-referencing between governance-defined land-use categories and biophysical indicators.

S2.5.2 Structural characteristics of forest integrity

The supplementary spatial analysis confirms that the Maikiuants territory is characterised by a dominant forest matrix (Table S2.5.1) organised in a largely continuous configuration (Figure S2.5.1).

Table S2.5.1. Area by Land Use Category within the Maikiuants Territory

Category	Area (ha)	Percentage (%)
Strict conservation	8363	91.6%
Low use	269	2.9%
Sustainable use	447	4.9%
Infrastructure	34	0.4%
No information	13	0.2%
Total	9126	100%

⁷ See e.g. C. Voigt, *International Judicial Practice on the Environment* (CUP 2019) (on ecological integrity as a legal standard).

⁸ Ecuadorian Constitutional Court jurisprudence emphasising preventive protection of Nature; see e.g. *Los Cedros* case (Judgment No. 1149-19-JP/21).

Clasificación de Uso de Suelo-Maikiuants

Figure S2.5.1. Unsupervised classification (K-means) of land-use categories based on community-defined classifications, illustrating spatial patterns and clustering of land-use types across the study area.

The analytical focus here is on structural properties of the landscape, rather than aggregate coverage values. Three features are of particular relevance; i) Continuity: Conservation and low-use zones form an extensive, contiguous forest system with limited internal fragmentation, ii) Low anthropogenic footprint: Infrastructure occupies a marginal proportion of the territory, reducing edge formation and barrier effects, iii) Governance-aligned zoning: Land-use categories derived from the Shuar Arutam Life Plans correspond closely to observed patterns of low-intensity use and conservation-oriented management⁹. Taken together, these characteristics indicate a high degree of landscape connectivity and limited exposure to fragmentation dynamics. The supplementary material clarifies that these conditions are not incidental but are structured through formalised Indigenous territorial governance.

S2.5.3 EVRoN interpretative considerations

The additional analysis supports four clarifications relevant to the EVRoN framework.

First, the legal significance of forest integrity arises not solely from its extent, but from its spatial coherence. Continuous forest systems are more susceptible to non-linear degradation effects

⁹ 'Plan de Vida PSHA Version Digital 2016-2026 | PDF', Scribd, accessed 26 May 2026, <https://es.scribd.com/document/1010484091/Plan-de-Vida-PSHA-Version-Digital-2016-2026>.

when fragmented, thereby reinforcing a preventive standard under Article 71. The evidentiary relevance lies in the system's susceptibility to threshold disruption.

Second, the spatial correspondence between governance zoning and ecological condition substantiates the interpretative linkage between Articles 71 and 74. Forest integrity is maintained through collective territorial management practices, indicating that constitutional protection is operationalised through institutional arrangements rather than existing independently of them.

Third, the observed landscape configuration is consistent with requirements for ecological connectivity at the ecosystem scale. The supplementary analysis emphasises structural connectivity (continuity, absence of barriers, low edge density) as a legally relevant attribute, providing the basis for precautionary evaluation of fragmentation risks.¹⁰

Fourth, the analysis refines the characterisation of cross-boundary effects. The Warintz River and the proposed export road constitute functional connectivity pathways through which impacts may be transmitted into the territory. These pathways are significant not as discrete project components, but as mechanisms facilitating indirect, cumulative, and spatially extended effects. As such, they bring the territory within the material ambit of potential impact notwithstanding its exclusion from the formal Area of Influence.

S2.5.4 Interim conclusion

The supplementary evidence confirms that the Maikiuants territory constitutes a structurally coherent and functionally connected forest system maintained through Indigenous governance. The analytical contribution of this section lies in specifying the attributes of connectivity, spatial organisation, and governance alignment that underpin this condition. From a constitutional perspective, three implications follow:

1. **Preventive standard of protection:** The integrity and continuity of the system elevate the obligation to avoid initial disturbance under Articles 71 and 73;
2. **Constitutional relevance of governance systems:** Indigenous territorial planning operates as a legally significant mechanism for maintaining ecological integrity within the meaning of Article 74;
3. **Expanded scope of impact assessment:** The presence of hydrological and infrastructural connectivity necessitates consideration of indirect, cumulative, and cross-boundary effects.

Accordingly, the supplementary analysis reinforces the appropriateness of an ecosystem-scale, precautionary approach grounded in prevention and *in dubio pro natura*^{10,15}. Particular weight should be accorded to processes capable of disrupting landscape connectivity, including linear

¹⁰ Ecuadorian constitutional principle of *in dubio pro natura*, recognised in Constitutional Court jurisprudence (e.g. *Los Cedros* case).

infrastructure development, hydrological alteration, and induced deforestation dynamics, irrespective of formal project boundaries.

S2.6 Landscape and biome scale connectivity (EVRoN–Biome): supporting datasets and analytical inputs

S2.6.1 Landscape context and forest cover

The Warintza project area is located within the Cordillera del Cóndor region of the south-eastern Ecuadorian Amazon, characterised by continuous tropical forest cover and high landscape connectivity. Remote sensing indicators derived from Global Forest Watch (GFW) at the canton scale (Limón Indanza) indicate relatively low recent forest loss within the immediate project area compared with regional averages and high continuity of forest cover across surrounding landscapes. These data provide a spatial context for landscape-scale connectivity, including habitat continuity and potential for species movement.

S2.6.2 Tailings facility parameters

Table S2.6.1. Key physical characteristics of the proposed tailings facility after year 22 in the EIA.

Parameter	Reported value
Total tailings volume	~1.3 billion tonnes
Estimated stored volume	~650–870 million m ³
Spatial footprint	~8.35 km ²
Impoundment height (average)	~78–105 m
Operational lifespan	~22 years
Waste rock classification	~75% potentially acid generating

The proposed tailings facility represents a large-scale, long-duration containment structure, with dimensions substantially exceeding those reported for multiple historical tailings facilities.

S2.6.3 Seismic hazard parameters

The project is located within a high seismic hazard zone (NEC Zone V) under the Ecuadorian Construction Code.

Table S2.6.2. Seismic hazard characteristics of the project area identified in the EIA.

Parameter	Reported value
Seismic hazard classification	NEC Zone V
Design peak ground acceleration	~0.41–0.50 g
Maximum credible earthquake magnitude	Mw 7.5–7.7
Potential peak ground motion	up to ~0.65 g

The EIA identifies earthquakes as credible hazards but does not report (i) quantified seismic stability analyses, (ii) liquefaction modelling, (iii) failure consequence modelling linked to seismic loading. Seismic hazard parameters indicate high-energy ground motion potential, with limited quantitative modelling details provided in the EIA.

S2.6.4 Comparative tailings facility characteristics

Table S2.6.3. Comparative characteristics of tailings facilities

Parameter	Brumadinho (2019)	Fundão/Mariana (2015)	Warintza (proposed)
Stored volume (m³)	~12 million	~43 million	650–870 million
Spatial footprint (km²)	~0.25	~1	~8.35
Height / thickness	86 m	~110 m	~78–105 m

The proposed Warintza facility has a substantially larger stored volume and footprint than the comparator sites.